

**TEACHING ENGLISH AS A LANGUAGE
OF COMMUNICATION TO ADULT STUDENTS:
CASE OF UEA, LANGUAGE RESOURCE CENTER**

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Abstract

Language is essentially a means of communication among the members of a society. The purpose of this article is to show the importance of communication skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing skills) in the classroom in order to get a perfect acquisition of the second language. These skills are really connected and it is important to put into practice together and integrate them with the classroom activities. After my experience as assistant lecturer, I have noticed that these skills are very important parts in relation to the acquisition of English, I have also asked my students in order to know their thoughts in relation to my hypothesis, and they assure that these skills need to be developed. Students need to know how to be a good listener or speaker, because if they travel abroad, they are going to communicate through listening and speaking skills but not reading or writing only. For DRC French speakers, listening and speaking English tend to be more complicated than the acquisition of other skills, such as reading or writing, since the former are quite difficult to practice when the students do not live in an English speaking country. It is because of this reason that this article deals with some activities to develop with the adult students in order to develop these skills and show why it is important to be developed and the difficulties the learners have. The need to communicate has been focused on and this need arises and becomes stronger and stronger when one has someone else to communicate with. Communication must take place not only in the classroom but also outside the classroom. The language has to be practiced enough by taking into account those skills.

Keywords: language, communication skills, difficulties, practice activities, importance, teaching and learning

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1. Introduction

Teaching English as a language of communication requires some steps in order to make the language more communicative. This study will explore how to integrate and exploit communication skills as a complement of inside grammar, vocabulary and as a way of improving the English level of adult students through a series of motivating activities and techniques suggested. However, Language is essentially a means of communication among the members of a society. In the expression of culture, language is a fundamental aspect. As for Julie S. Amberg and Deborah J. Vause (1978), language reflects both the individual characteristics of a person, as well as the beliefs and practices of his or her community. Languages are rule-governed systems made up of signs, so for an outsider to learn the language of a community, he or she must learn which signs are meaningful and which are not. Millions of French Language adult students today want to learn and improve their command of English or to ensure that their training of English achieve a good command of it. According to Robert Scholes (1985), what students [...] need is the kind of knowledge and skill that will enable them to make sense of their worlds, to determine their own interests, both individual and collective, to see through the manipulations of all sorts of texts in all sorts of media, and to express their views in some appropriate manner. Opportunities to learn English are provided in many different ways such as through formal instruction, travel and study abroad, as well as through the media and the Internet. The worldwide demand for English has created an enormous demand for quality language teaching and language teaching materials and resources. They want to be able to master English to a high level of accuracy and fluency. Employers, too, insist that their employees have good English language skills, and fluency in English is a prerequisite for success and advancement in many fields of employment in today's world. The demand for an appropriate teaching methodology is therefore as strong as ever.

In this article, the researcher will examine the methodology known as communicative language teaching, and explore the assumptions it is based on and how it can influence approaches to language teaching. In this case, research will have a look at the following:

- How do adult learners learn English language?
- What are adult learners and teachers' roles in the classroom interaction?
- Are there kinds of classroom activities that best facilitate learning?

Adult learners have great problems of translation and whatever answer they give originate from their known language expression before it is given to their teacher of English. Their debates and conversation are almost oriented to (L1) French language styles and expressions. Language learning is viewed as a process of mechanical habit training. Good habits are formed by having adult students produce correct sentences and not through making mistakes. Errors are to be avoided through controlled opportunities for production (either written or spoken). By memorizing dialogues and performing debates or conversations, the chances of making mistakes are minimized.

As Meyers and Jones (1993) assert, learning is truly meaningful only when learners have taken knowledge and made it their own. Learning is very much seen as under the control of the teacher.

Learners and teachers' roles to play are enormous in the classroom since the language is a communicative activity. Learners have to participate in classroom activities that are based on a cooperative rather than individualistic approach to learning. They have to become comfortable with listening to their peers in group work or pair work tasks, rather than relying on the teacher for a model. They are expected to take on a greater degree of responsibility for their own learning. And teachers have to assume the role of facilitator and monitor. Rather than being a model for correct speech and writing and one with the primary responsibility of making students produce plenty of error-free sentences, the teacher has to develop a different view of learners' errors and of her/his own role in facilitating language learning. This may promote and facilitate communication in the classroom learning process.

Classroom activities that teacher should avail for the benefit of adult students have to allow them to express freely their feelings and possible needs so as to become users of the English language. Focus should be made on mastering of different grammatical items and practice through controlled activities such as memorization of conversations, dialogues and debates. As Kimberly Nance (2010) states: Students need to read for themselves, think critically about what they read, and then express and develop their responses through discussing and writing. The use of pair work activities, role plays, project work and group work activities should be carried out for adult students' improvement in language classroom communication. Analyzing classroom text either speaking or written one in order to improve and check students' vocabulary and grammatical competence as well as communicative one.

This article is limited to the presentation of results, analysis and findings of the different communicative teaching and learning that teachers and learners use in the adults English classrooms.

The results of this article will be helpful in English language teaching and learning. Teachers and researchers who will be in need to know different communicative language teaching used and come across in adult English language classrooms will refer to this article as a source.

2. Review of literature

The communication is the part of the live of human being. According to the explanation of psychologists communication is the form of public relations through which an exchange of ideas and interests are maintained. In order to achieve the goal in active interaction, the subject will relate with an object.

It is difficult for teachers to design adult students' course and implement activity for effectively communication, and it is difficult for students to foster the communicative process, especially if they do not have the skills to make effective use of

communication. According to Jack C. Richards (1979), to give a detailed account of what they mean by “communicative,” explanations vary widely’. To learn English language for communication depends on the time and energy learners and teacher have managed for learning and teaching but also the materials availed. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cultural_communication, Learners of a language have to use it as a means of communication for cultural values.

In the communication process, two or more individuals are involved: speaker (A 1 addressee) and listener (A 2- addressees). To establish communication and language act, the topic of the speech (D) should be set up. At the same time, the communication goes with language (L). To engage with the topic (D), the participant (A1), expresses opinion to the addressee (A2). And this process is carried by means of language (L).

To this scheme can be included communication style, as a key component of a communication. People communicate daily. To cooperate with representatives of other cultures there is not enough that know only language. In the process of communication there can appear cultural misunderstanding on base of body language and facial expression. This kind of misunderstanding between the communicators leads to culture shock.

Therefore, the communicator has to know the worldview, the values, and the correct etiquette. Communication culture should be known by every communicator as it results with correct communication. Following the etiquette norms communicators show adequate attitude of speaker to the listener also is one of the preconditions of successful communication.

Scientist and journalist R. Syzdyk say that “*Language culture is the correct use of words (lexical), correct structure (syntax), the correct fitting (morphology), right pronunciation (orthoepy), correct writing (spelling), vivid use of language (linguasylistic) standards should be established and improved*”.

Language is the most important tool which covers every aspect of human life. Cultural values can be saved in word stock, grammar, phrases, proverbs, folklore, art and scientific literature oral and written forms of the speech. The culture of speech is set of requirements of the characteristics belonged to specific culture. Etiquette is a historical phenomenon. Depending on the dynamic change, rules of people's behaviour will be varying in accordance with the requirements of the time. Etiquette appeared at the same time with monarchy. The career and life of the person were depended on how the person obeyed the rules.

Moreover, all people subconsciously mirror their cultural backgrounds in day-to-day communication. Language is both a great advocate for communication and an important reflection of one's cultural background. Intra-cultural "miscommunication often stems from different and conflicting styles of speech and messages.

According to http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cultural_communication, *"connotations of words, as well as meanings of slang phrases, vary greatly across cultural lines, and a lack of tolerance and understanding of this fact often results in misinterpretations."* There is a close relationship between the language and the culture of a community - they are inextricably related, so that one cannot understand or appreciate the one without a good knowledge of the other. Culture may reflect in body language, customs, superstitions, and even expressions of friendliness. Although all these definitely observe the cultural norms of a particular society, the impact of culture on language use is both deep and thorough. In this context, culture refers to the lifestyle of a community: the way its members behave, their beliefs, their values and, most importantly, the way they communicate.

For <http://www.thefreedictionary.com/dialect>, sociolinguistic research has documented the existence of dialects in every language. Dialects are usually associated with educational, economic, social and historical circumstances. Linguistically, the word "dialect" is referred to as a regional or social variety of a language distinguished by pronunciation, grammar, or vocabulary, especially a variety of speech differing from the standard literary language or speech pattern of the culture in which it exists and not to an incorrect way of speaking a language. While diversifying in terms of space (languages, dialects, idioms), or time, language is also dependent on the social characters of speakers (jargon, slang, specialised terminology) and their anthropological affiliation (child or teenager language, men and women language). Sociolinguistics studies social and cultural influences on language behaviour. Among the most significant aspects are the ones pertaining to dialects and language standards.

People learn a language for communication in order to express their feelings or emotions. Ghosh (2009) states learning a language means becoming able to use it to comprehend, communicate, and think – as they do in their first language.

Those who study language may disagree with a precise definition of a language due to some concepts, such as whether or not language must have a written and/or oral component, one can agree that language is a rule-based system of signs. Saying that

language is rule-based usually, makes people think of other kinds of situations where rules are enforced by a particular authority.

For example, if someone may think about classroom behaviour. Learners are expected to sit still, be quiet, pay attention, and so on; typically, there are consequences if they don't follow these rules. Language rules are not enforced by any authority figure; language police does not exist. Language rules are conventions. This means that they come into existence through common practice by users of the language rather than through the imposition of an authority figure. Members who use the language conventions of their particular community may not even be conscious of following them.

Taking into consideration in all that, language is as a system of rules or conventions because a single language convention, for example, a single word, a pause, or an alphabet letter, does not tell us much beyond its immediate meaning. Thus, we usually combine these conventions together to convey larger meanings.

To teach and learn a language for communication to adult learners of French we have to follow some strategies after selecting their needs in order to become good communicators of the language.

This article will focus on listening and speaking, writing and reading skills about adult students at UEA. Those skills will be combined with grammar and vocabulary as a way of helping students to understand the language system and to develop their ability by using them to communicate successfully inside and outside the classroom.

3. Methodology

This study has looked at the level of communication of 73 students who are enrolled in different levels: Beginners 1 & 2, and Intermediates 1 & 2. Among the participants, 50 of them are males and 23 are females.

All of the students have studied English since they joined the secondary school but, in general, their level is low, with some exceptions and their everyday working language is French.

The main aim of this study is to analyze the students' attitudes and opinions towards communication skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing). The followed methodology has been accomplished through a three-stage investigation.

The first stage consisted of the observation of the development of the English lesson in order to check to what extent four skills are carried out in the classroom. During the observation, it was discovered that a great part of the time of each lesson was devoted to the study of the grammatical structures followed by the corresponding exercises to practice what they had learnt. Consequently, listening and speaking skills are hardly practiced due to there is not enough time left.

Besides, there are other factors, which prevent from developing these two skills such as the short of time of students in learning and the impossibility of using English individually during their every day working.

As a second stage, the teacher is interviewed with the purpose of knowing how he confronts four skills, the way he organizes and structures the lessons and the solutions he proposes to put them into practice successfully.

It is considered that it is important to take into account the opinion and ideas of the participants' teachers of this research because they are the persons who plan and design the activities in every English lesson.

The sort of listening activities that learners usually do depend on their level, that is, students from beginner one and two have a lower level than students from intermediate one and two.

The most typical exercises carried out in class are: fill in the gaps, True or False, comprehension questions, complete information in the chart or matching exercises.

Furthermore, songs are funny listening activities for the adult students and teachers used them as an excuse to revise grammar or vocabulary and sometimes, they are used as the base for writing too.

Obviously, in spite of the kind of exercises chosen by the teacher, students are given some clues about what they are going to listen and are also encouraged to read the questions or the instructions before starting listening.

Another remarkable thing when we talk about adult students is that, apart from the English language they use in class, they seldom listen to it very often. Only some adult students in intermediate assure that they are very keen on audio-visual materials, TV series in English but they watch them with subtitles rarely due to limited time. The main problems observed by the teacher when adult students are listening to English are lack of concentration and lack of practice. They do not usually train their ear and they do not know how to improve this skill because they need to get used to listen to English to develop their capacities.

The more practice they do, the better results they will obtain.

Having mentioned the types of activities students do during their English lessons and also the problems and obstacles they have when they have to listen to English, what is the best solution to help them?

It is necessary to anticipate them what the listening will be about by paying attention to questions, pictures... and also to introduce them any difficult vocabulary. Moreover, as a new tool, the teacher is trying to send students some listening activities as homework due to almost all textbooks are accompanied by the corresponding CD and it is a way to practice this skill if teachers have not got enough time to do it in class. The teacher generally encourages students to watch TV with subtitles even if they do not understand, only with the purpose of training and developing their ear.

Up to now, it has been discussed what happens with listening in the classroom but, how about speaking?

The major problems the teacher finds when adult students try to speak in English are: on the one hand, as they do not listen to a lot of English, their amount of grammar and vocabulary is not wide enough. On the other hand, they feel embarrassed and they find it really difficult.

In general, they do not pay much attention to pronunciation and most of them feel frustrated when they know they are making mistakes all the time. It is true that all problems have a solution and the teacher thinks that the best one is to encourage students to speak English as much as possible.

They have opportunities to speak it when they meet foreigners (via Internet or travelling abroad), in class or with their friends from abroad. Sometimes, the teacher tries to create situations where English is needed and also gives them some fixed sentences that students can say, so that they feel more comfortable and improve little by little.

The last stage comprises two sections: a survey which consisted of a series of questions that adult students had to answer expressing their opinion and some listening, writing, reading and speaking activities which were carried out in the classroom to prove their effectiveness in helping adult students to improve their abilities in relation to these skills.

On the one hand, the survey is formed by twelve questions, which deal with the students' management of the English language referring to communicative skills.

On the other hand, the reading, writing, listening and speaking activities proposed intend to help students to develop and improve their abilities and capacities and to give them facilities in order to feel confident when they are communicating in English language in the class.

4. Presentation of Results, Description and Analysis

Taking into account the results obtained through the study, can be said that the four skills are important, which must be taught thoroughly in order to confront them as they do with other skills such as they do with grammar.

The first stage of the research demonstrates that it is very difficult to develop these skills because it is necessary to devote more time to them to do a suitable practice with all the students.

The second stage offers the teacher's overview regarding communication skills. It is proved that they are important as he tries to include them in his syllabus design day by day even though it is difficult due to many factors. The most important one is the lack of time, which prevents to develop interesting activities, to teach many useful expressions and to assess them in a proper way to confirm if they have been suitably learnt.

The third stage consists of an interview to compile students' opinions about the use and the comprehension of English in class and in their daily life. Analyzing them, it is demonstrated that most of the students are aware of the importance of acquiring these skills but they show their lack of confidence when exposing themselves to the language.

So, through several questions contained in the survey, students reflected their thoughts in relation to these skills that allowed us to study their problems and

difficulties in learning listening and speaking skills more than in reading and writing ones.

a. Reading

The skill of reading facilitates to assess students' pronunciation both in class and in the test situation. Reading often involves multiple processes in which the reader is actively engaged. For example, a question may test students' comprehension of a paragraph. The teacher can give such a kind of Assignment to read:

“English is now used by millions of speakers for a number of communicative functions across many countries. It has become the preferred language in a number of ambits like international business. Time and again it is also the language chosen for academic discussion as most scholars face the need to read and publish in English for international diffusion”

Here, a typical sequence of skills application and the impact on the successful outcome of the task is illustrated below:

- Student A is unable to decode the words within the sentence, so cannot answer the question
- Student B can decode, read the paragraph for meaning, understands the question correctly and gives the right answer
- Student C's working memory is fully occupied with reading words and sentences, which leaves no 'brain space' for comprehension
- Student D understands the paragraph but does not understand the questions and comes to the answer

The above analysis engages the students in a sequence of four processes which only produce the correct answer if the learner manages all of them. Thus, reading is not just a complex process for the reader, it is also challenging for the teacher or test setter. This is because test items are only effective if they are set with a clear understanding of their purpose and of the skills which are being tested. In my experience as a teacher, learners feel bewildered by the range of scores they get for practice and exam tests. Even those who take and pass a difficult exam feel deflated if their score are low.

b. Listening, speaking and writing

These skills are not easy to be separated because they are almost assessed at the same moment. According to Bueno, Madrid and McLaren (2006), listening is important for speaking because it establishes the good basis for successful communicative exchanges. There are several activities that integrate listening-comprehension, writing with speaking:

- Integrated skills work (jigsaw-listening, for example): This involves the pupils working together to share heard information. First two to four groups of pupils separately listen to different recording on the same subjects, i.e. the same journey with some differences in each version. A choice of various activities may follow, but for example, one may be a tape script with spaces that the learners have to

fill in. They then tell it individually to a learner from the other group (s) and try to find the differences. The paper is not used at all, as it is now the speaking skill that is highlighted for integration with the initial listening – comprehension and post-reading practice.

- Using video: Video clips may be watched and enjoyed and then be followed by a discussion on understanding the cultural information inherent in them. This may be highlighted and discussed in the class among students.
- Using the language laboratory: These offer not only an opportunity for the customary oral drills but also phonological recognition and discrimination, extensive listening and oral vocabulary but also writing skills (the student writes down what he/she is listening).
- Using computers and CD-ROMs: Computers offer the possibility of being used at home as further-practice incorporating listening to English. CD-ROMs also have the audio facilities for listening-activity which can lead even a learner to imitation in order to develop speaking skills and so do some web pages.
- Using pop songs (probably the most popular listening activity with secondary pupils). These could be extremely popular at Secondary level, probably the most popular activity if the teacher knows how to select up-to-date songs that are also clearly pronounced, as well as being useful in some way didactically. When songs are chosen carefully, many skills can be integrated with them: sound to spelling recognition (via gap filling activities), oral practice, topics for discussion and debates, etc.
- During games: Games make students to learn from another. There is reciprocal learning on the part of game makers. They practice language at the same time of the game.
- Listening as homework: It allows student to become a good listener and able to get messages from native speaker. This is not so much about speaking skills as further opportunity for listening-practice. It is rarely done by many secondary school teachers in our area. Some centers have copies of cassettes, videos or films available for loan from their library. A special learner-tape for extra practice accompanies some course books.

In the same way that a good writer is a good reader, a good speaker is also a good listener. This rule is generally applicable to second language learners and it has to do with the correlation between productive (writing and speaking) and receptive (reading and listening) skills Bueno, Madrid and McLaren, (2005).

The above activities integrate communication because the songs, videos or listening text-topic is the keyboard for a discussion, drill or pronunciation practice. Integrated activities also provide opportunities for much needed students behavioral-interaction described by Lynch (1997) earlier. Dictations integrate listening and speaking. Although they have not been, very fashionable dictations are at the moment once again seen as relevant. Dictations may also be used as a means to evaluate student's listening comprehension, as long as the scoring is carefully done.

4.1 Speaking activities

The following exercises should be organized in the way that the teacher should talk to the learner and the learner to the others as follows:

A.

T: "I'm a teacher. I'm a teacher of English."

T: "Who are you?" **S:** "I'm Olive. I'm a student."

T: "Where are from?" **S:** "I'm from Costa Rica."

T: "What is your name?" **S:** "It's Olive." **S1:** "Is your friend from Iran"? **S2:** "No, he is from Iraq. He's studying English."

S3: "Is Bali studying English too?" **S2:** "No, she's studying Economics. She's from DRC." **S4:** "Are your parents teachers too?"

S2: "No, they are not, they are farmers." **S5:** "Who help them to cultivate"?

S2: "They always help themselves. We use to go to school."

B.

T: "Good morning class." **P:** "Good morning teacher."

T: "How many are you in class today?" **P:** "Today we are twenty-five."

T: "Are there any girls in our classroom." **P:** "Yes, they are."

T: "How many are they?" **P:** "They are five."

T: "Are they all present?" **P:** "No, a few of them are present." **T:** "Are all those girls intelligent?" **P:** "No, only few are."

Speaking is a complex process that involves constructing a message in order to other people can understand and deliver the message using the correct pronunciation, stress and intonation. It also involves interaction and to do this, learners must be able to respond what other people say. At the same time, they need to be accurate and fluent enough for the other person to understand.

To be able to do all of these mentioned, students need lots of practice, encouragement and correction. In order to exploit speaking, there are a lot of different activities to practice and reinforce it with students but the following ones shown below are examples, which allowed us to practice speaking during the English lessons and to carry out the study related to the students' attitudes and problems through speaking:

a. Speaking out activities

Debate (completion between 2 groups of people):

PRO: "A man must obey his wife at all times."

CON: "A man is not responsible for obeying his wife."

The teacher's focus is to control language processing among his students by checking the four language skills. The class chooses four students to be a panel of "experts". They come and sit in a row facing the class after choosing a topic that they are going to have to be experts on (four who are PRO and four CON).

b. Listening activities:

1. Conversation 1: listening 1 At the Travel Agent and Do you like school

2. Conversation 2: listening 2 Making a date and listening 5 I borrow a pen
3. Conversation 3: listening 3 At the Airport and At the Hotel
4. Conversation 4: listening 4 Did you type those Reports?

How well did you understand MOST of the English you listened to while learning English conversation?

1. What happened first?
2. What happened next?
3. After that, what happened?
4. What happened at the end of the listening?

Such a kind of exercises may help learners to improve their listening and speaking skills and may help them to become familiar with native speakers of English language for communicative purposes.

c. Writing activities

In writing activities, the learner is confronted to the use of listening combined with writing. Almost the four skills of a language can be tackled if the teacher wants to deal with them in classroom composition. For example write about your educational background and record it on a CD. The teacher can dictate also a text to be written by his learners in order to test their language competence. For example: Write down the following paragraph:

“English is now used by millions of speakers for a number of communicative functions across many countries. It has become the preferred language in a number of ambits like international business. Time and again it is also the language chosen for academic discussion as most scholars face the need to read and publish in English for international diffusion”

After dictation, the teacher can ask ones of his students to pass in front of the class and write down the text as required. Then the teacher makes correction together with his students on the black board.

Table 1: Communication for investigated adult students in learning English

Communication activities or skills	Yes %	No %
1. Listening and understanding English songs	23	77
2. Classroom communication in English	89	11
3. Outside communication in English (at work)	12	88
4. Understand a native speaker	33	67
5. Watch English movies / films	7	93
6. Listen English programs	63	57
7. English clubs or events	3	97
8. Classroom audio-visual materials	87	13
9. Outside classroom audio-visual materials	18	82

In the above table, one may read that most of the respondents (87%) assure that classroom audio-visual materials are more appreciated by adult students during their English lessons out of a 13 per cent of students. They say that they like to follow native speakers in order to improve their pronunciation and to feel familiar with the second language they are learning. They do not follow audio-visual materials outside classroom due to lack of time of concentration outside the classroom. Simply a few numbers of students, that is, 18 per cent out of an 88 per cent students like to follow outside classroom audio-visual materials. The majority is in contact or use English in the classroom instead of practicing it even outside the classroom.

Only a 23 per cent of the respondents feel capable of listening and understanding English songs whereas a 77 per cent is unable to listening and understanding English songs. Some respondents listen to songs in English understanding what it is about but others state that they can learn by heart the song whereas they do not know what it is saying or how to spell the words of the lyrics. A number of 89 per cent communicate or speak English in the classroom with some difficulties and can maintain a conversation in English in five minutes but 11 per cent feel afraid of uttering wrong words in front of others.

In relation to the possibility of understanding a native speaker, the results are very varied. Some of the students (33%) think that they would understand a native speaker but a 67 per cent consider that it results very difficult or almost impossible.

They admit that they usually listen to their teacher and, in some cases; they listen to the CD player only in the classroom. A possibility to solve this problem would be to invite native speakers to come to their English lesson and interact with them. A small number of students watch English movies or films a 7 per cent out of 93 percent of students who are not interested on them. The use of English language outside the classroom is very rare, only 12 percent of students communicate sometimes in English whereas 88 percent seem to neglect to communicate in it during their every day work or activities.

A few of the participants (3%) declare that they sometimes participate to English club events but 97 per cent do not partake due to time constraint and lack of motivation since their secondary school studies. As for listening or watching English program, a 63 per cent do it out of a 57 per cent of students. English Television or Radio programs can help students to improve their language because they understand better, what that program is about or what the characters are saying.

Finally, the above activities may be integrated in the teaching process in order to favour students' improvement and motivation. These elements should allow even learner to feel all the time on learning duties even outside their classroom.

5. Findings

- First of all, teachers should use the English language from Primary Education so, if pupils are accustomed to this language since an early age, it will be easier to communicate and understand English better and their fears will disappear.
- Nowadays, there are few private schools where teachers do this, and the results are very good although recently, the situation has improved due to the creation of bilingual schools and extra classes in English but it is still necessary do more for the future, if Congolese want to obtain similar levels of English as many other countries.
- Different activities or assignments should be implemented in different levels of the English language.
- Culture of making dialogues or debate should be everyday language communication activities.
- It is suitable to create a confident atmosphere in order to improve students' English language, for this reason, most activities elicit students to share ideas, opinions and experiences with each other.
- Doing more activities outside school, participating in events or inviting people from an English speaking country as a way of comprehending its practical use.
- Another way would be using new technologies, which are very useful and motivate the students because they consider them something different and funny.
- Teachers must support students in their education and encourage them to use English, and at the same time, teachers need to be in constant contact with new techniques and materials in this changeable teaching world.
- Teaching English as a language of communication can be very different depending on the methodology followed by each teacher but what it is really important is to develop during the English lessons to get students learn the second language entirely.
- Teachers are required to insist on communicative principles in order to achieve the language acquisition objective and communication skills.

6. Conclusion

This research has tried to show that it is easier to obtain adult students' participation and motivation when the suggested materials are entertaining, original and surprising. The objective is to motivate and change their negative attitude towards English giving adult students a chance to speak about interesting topics, which can result easy for them and for their level. According to the results obtained, we can notice that communication competences are complex that need to be developed consciously. They can best be developed with practice in classroom through activities, which promote interaction between adult students. It is only when adult student spontaneously uses

vocabulary or expresses his own opinion related to listening or reading aloud carried out in the classroom that he comes familiar to language.

An idea would be giving adult students opportunities to use their speaking and listening skills in real life situations, giving them the sense of what they are learning in situations that they do not have in the classroom. For example: practicing more activities outside school, participating in events or English clubs, inviting people from English speaking countries for exchanging experience. Another way would be using new technologies, which are very useful and motivate the adult students because they consider them something different and funny.

It is desirable to say that teachers must support students in their education and encourage them to use English, and at the same time, teachers need to be in constant contact with new techniques and materials in this changeable teaching world. Teaching writing, reading listening and speaking skills can be very different depending on the methodology followed by each teacher but what it is really important is to develop during the English lessons to get students learn the second language entirely.

The classroom activities and home assignments allow adult students to feel more comfortable and sure when they have to hold a conversation in English and they make the skills more effective in order to get a perfect acquisition of the second language, covering all the skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing. Due to this, some suggestions have been offered, which can be put into practice during the lesson in order to motivate students to participate in class and to do interaction activities to develop communicative skills.

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